

Integrating Machine Learning and Multiscale Modeling—Advances, Challenges and Future Possibilities

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ABSTRACT

The advancements of machine learning have created an opportunity for integrating multimodality, multifidelity data and revealing connections between intertwined phenomena. Although machine learning has been successfully applied in the automation of the process of analysis of data, shortening the time for making decision, as well as ensuring high accuracy and repeatability of results, it disregards fundamental physical rules, which might lead to ill-posed issues or non-physical solutions. Multiscale modeling on the other hand, has shown to be an effective technique for integrating multiscale, multiphysics data and uncovering mechanisms that underlie the genesis of function. However, multiscale modeling alone frequently fails to efficiently mix huge datasets from many sources and resolution levels. This minisymposium investigates how machine learning and multiscale modeling may naturally complement one another to provide strong prediction models that incorporate the underlying physics to manage ill-posed issues and explore vast design areas. Topics may include the application of AI in different fields, with the emphasis of how machine learning and multiscale modeling mutually complement one another, interact at the parameter level by restricting parameter spaces, identifying parameter values, exploiting underlying physics, constraining design spaces, and discovering system dynamics.

Key words: machine learning, multiscale modelling, deep learning, data mining, expert systems